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Deliverable 5.1

Website

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SUMMARY

Deliverable 5.1 involves applications in communications and open access in order to publicate widely within dissemination and exploitation activities. To provide these activities the structure and the design of the Bio-Acouis web site which is already launched as online and available. Moreover, the project website will provide most of the data progressed (in particular reports, scientific publications, demonstration activities and other dissemination materials). The project website as a result of Deliverable 5.1 aims to:

- The project website will be headquarters and sharepoint to participant and audiences.
- The project web portal will make the project's progress and outcomes visible to the public.
- The website is an important tool in the dissemination to the R&D community and industry.

The website will be set up to organize the main information of the participants and their work, regularly up-dating the available data in terms of publications and communications. News will be also published in partner websites.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Objective

Bio-Acouis, a project funded through the European Union's Horizon 2021 research and innovation programme under grant agreement (No:101086325 Bio-Acouis) the project which will provide acoustic solutions made by bio-based materials.

Bio-Acouis intends to reinforce research and experimental develop activities in cutting-edge technologies moreover, results will contribute to the R&D community and commercial sectors. Eventually, the promising project will create the structure which will contribute actions to develop communication strategies between stakeholders.

The project tasks involves the Work Packages which describes fundamental obligations of consortium members during the project date. These activities will be executed throughout the project and ER researcher will involve in terms of to ensure effective dissemination and exploitation of the results and collaboration, both during and after completion of joint activities. A work package on Dissemination and Outreach activities (WP5) has been considered in order to carry out the internal and external activities related to the project. The main objective of WP5, as described in the Grant Agreement, is to create consciousness of the project, stimulate dissemination of the project results and organize dissemination actions. In order to meet these objectives, the available existing communication tools will be used, and a series of activities will be organized.

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Deliverable D5.1 describes the key points of design, execution, content, usage, and communication strategy behind the internet platform of the Bio-Acouis project.

The URL of the website is www.bio-acouis.eu and it has gone live mid February 2023 and also visible for search engines. The website is hosted and maintained by Coordinator, BURO and it will be updated regularly. The website constitutes a key communication tool to

increase project visibility and impact towards industrial communities, researchers and general public. It is also a key tool for sharing information between all partners.

Rationale

Bio-Acouis Website is visualization and communication tool which is presents to public with relating to all documentations and information, interesting news and events throughout all relevant scientific and industrial sectors. It will include public area information about the project, its objectives, project partners, concerning outputs achieved, the events and relevant news, useful links; downloads of Bio-Acouis e-newsletters and relevant documents. Internal area will be accessible only by partners, covering relevant information, documents, outputs, results, data exchange space and tools etc. Other communications methos and activities such as newsletter, brochures etc. has described in grant agreement WP5 description, which also will use on website with stated documents.

2. LOGO

The project logo is an integral part of the brand as it is included in all project promotional material. The Bio-Acouis logo is designed using a combination of Project Name within nature concept such as renewable, eco-friendly, recycled etc. and related with sound wave indications in respect to acoustic features. The project logo also refers to environment and health with use of green in order to reflect the main concept of the Project.

The logo alternatives was voted by the consortium members on 27th of February 2023 during Kick-Off Meeting in Brussels. The feedback during voting has been used to revise, improve, support the idea of Bio-Acouis and symbolize the principals of Bio-Acouis by visualization.

Figure 1: Logo Illustrations of Potential Variations

Figure 2: Bio-Acouis Logo Final Edition

3. PROJECT WEBSITE

Bio-Acouis project website is the most important appliance to announce the project and disseminating objectives, work plan and results to a wide audience including all stakeholders and possible end-users. The Bio-Acouis website has been developed following the EU's best practice guidelines for project websites.

To ensure successful promotion of the project and to sustain the interest of the target audience and attract new users, the website's content will be maintained, continuously updated and populated with new information throughout the project's lifetime.

Bio-Acouis website is accessible at: www.bio-acouis.eu. The website has been created to serve as a project content management system on two levels:

1. For all users (Public): Contents are external communication and dissemination of the project objectives and results
2. Privacy Area: For only participants who have accessible to authority

The website structure has been selected to meet the requirements of EU Commission and follows an easy to use that allows to reach and explore the website easily. On the home page, the top menu bar contains sections of the website on Home, About Us, Project, News&Media, Contact. All users can reach contact form easily with Contact Button that will provide direct communication to coordinator and beneficiaries any time. Users may find directly Social Media Icons on the left-top side and right footer.

Bio-Acouis website has been designed on a green colour concept and main menu sections are considered to meet the requirements of dissemination activities the following main pages:

- **Home:** Website homepage gives general information about the project facts, purposes, expectations and preview. Menu bar includes directories to beneficiaries informations, project guidelines, news&media and contact sections, Homepage images can be seen in Figure 3 and Figure 4 below.

Figure 3: Project Website, Homepage

Figure 4: Project Website, Homepage

- **About Us:** defines general description of the project partners, including their role in the project and link to their websites for further information as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Project Website, About Us

Figure 6: Project Website, About Us

• **Project:** describes about project brief description, main objective, specific objective for each points, WPs descriptions, also download section will provide the project results and presented materials for both internal area and public area as illustrated in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

Figure 7: Project Website, Project

Figure 8: Project Website, Project

- **News&Media:** The news&media section will provide any news and events related to the Bio-Acouis project, as consortium meetings, workshops, participation at conferences, etc. Moreover, this section will give both project’s events and other events&media related with the project fields as illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Project Website, News&Media

- Contact:** This section will provide a contact channel between users and project representatives, Furthermore, if visitors intend to get extra information about the project, anyone can use e-mail addresses 'info@bio-acouis.eu' which will directly deliver their e-mail to all beneficiaries as illustrated in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

The screenshot shows a contact form on the bio-acouis website. At the top, there is a green navigation bar with the bio-acouis logo and menu items: HOME, ABOUT US, PROJECT, NEWS&MEDIA, CONTACT. Below the navigation bar, the contact form is titled 'Get in touch!' and includes the following elements:

- A 'Contact us!' section with an email icon and the address 'info@bio-acouis.eu'.
- A social media icon for 'bio-acouis.eu'.
- Input fields for 'YOUR NAME', 'YOUR EMAIL', and 'SUBJECT'.
- A larger text area for 'YOUR MESSAGE (OPTIONAL)'.
- A 'SUBMIT' button at the bottom of the form.

Figure 10: Project Website, Contact

Figure 11: Project Website, Contact

Project website and all the information (Project results, Events, News, Media etc.) it contains, will provide creating permanent, potent dissemination action to making publications for whom interested scientific activities. Moreover, the Project website includes private area for project consortium members within Data Management Plan in Deliverable 6.1 and 6.2. This section was established with username/password access, only accessible internally by Project participants. Main purpose is protect to sensitive project documentations, materials, deliverables and a Sharepoint hub about the project’s activities and results.

Figure 12: Log-in of dissemination level sensitive material

4. CONCLUSION

The aim of deliverable D5.1 was to develop ‘Website’ a strong dissemination tool raise widespread awareness of the project and its results amongst stakeholders and people who may interest. This report highlights the key work done to date (M2) in developing this tool to facilitate communication activities carried out by who responsible person throughout the project. The project website is the main point for dissemination of the project results and WP5 leader BURO is responsible for maintenance and up-to-date situation of the website.